

Geopolitical And Economic Evaluation Of Gwadar Port In The China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC)

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Abstract

From a geo-economic perspective, the importance of Gwadar to China and Pakistan is thoroughly discussed, taking into consideration geopolitical and economic factors. In order to analyse Gwadar port, the writers used the geo-economic technique, historical viewpoint, geographical and geopolitical considerations, and global development patterns. The writers looked at how it helped Pakistan and China develop as well as how it benefited those countries' economies. A geo-economic study is conducted to obtain a deeper and more thorough understanding of the economic relationship between China and Pakistan because geo-economics examines how geographical, political, and economic aspects in international relations affect one another. Therefore, improvements at the Gwadar Port could strengthen Pakistan's and China's economic stability. Pakistan's oil pipeline can now transport electricity and oil from the Middle East directly to China because Gwadar Port is already operating. Via the CPEC, not just oil but also goods from Central Asia, Europe, and the US will pass through Gwadar Port on their way to China. The CPEC program's development of Gwadar port has the potential to significantly increase Pakistan's capacity for marine trade while reducing its reliance on Karachi, the nation's present largest port, which is situated close to the India border. Since geo-economics takes into account how geographical, locational, geopolitical, and economic components of international relations interact, it is used to conduct a more extensive and thorough examination of the economic relationship between China and Pakistan. The goal of this study is to examine the development of the Gwadar port and the geo-economics implications for China and Pakistan.

Introduction

There are two important ports in Pakistan, Gwadar and Karachi, along its about 1046 km of coastline. On the eastern coast, close to the Indian border, is Karachi (Bhatti 2020). On the western coast of Pakistan, not far from Iran's Middle Eastern region, is a city called Gwadar. Due to its close proximity to several significant marine trade routes, Gwadar Port is located in a particularly beneficial geostrategic position in the region. These include the East Asian and Pacific Oceans, the Red Sea, the Strait of Hormuz, the Persian Gulf, and the Strait of Hormuz. Gwadar, which is situated in the Markland district of the Baluchistan region of Pakistan, was formerly a peaceful fishing hamlet. Baluchistan is a province that China values highly strategically, but its economic and social conditions are dire. The lowest gross domestic product (GDP) of any province or region in Pakistan is in Baluchistan, according to the most recent statistics available. Even though the province only contributes 4.3% of the country's GDP, its 400 US dollars per person per year per capita is more than twice as much as Pakistan's average per capita income (Gholizadeh & Madani 2020). Baluchistan has the lowest population density of any province in Pakistan, although making up around half of the country's total land area. Baluchistan, however, more than makes up for this with its beaches, minerals, and oil and gas resources. This is due to increased interest among investors as a result of easier access to the province's raw materials. Despite the fact that there are a ton of potential benefits, putting these concepts into practice in Pakistan is not without its difficulties. The growth of the CPEC is at risk, and external and internal challenges threaten to stop its forward momentum, according to academics. As a direct result of the escalating security concerns in the area, which have significantly hampered local business development, the province of Baluchistan has recently become one of Pakistan's most volatile areas. In 2018, terrorist attacks in Pakistan were among the highest of any country, with one of the highest rates worldwide. Seventy-five percent of all terrorist-related fatalities that took place worldwide in 2018 were caused by events in Afghanistan, Iraq, Nigeria, Somalia, and Pakistan. Tehrik-i-Taliban Pakistan (TTP), a branch of the Pakistani Taliban, perpetrated 56 attacks in 2017, resulting in 233 fatalities. A luxurious hotel in Gwadar that was crowded with tourists was assaulted by gunmen in the year 2019 (Gholizadeh & Madani 2020). The Pakistani government has struggled to keep a handle on its overall debt as

public and international obligations have risen considerably in recent years. The liabilities of Pakistan in 2018 totaled Rs 29.8 trillion, or 86% of its GDP (Haider 2018). Its debt-to-GDP ratio is higher than the 60% threshold imposed by the Fiscal Responsibility and Debt Limitation Act of 2005. The IMF anticipated that by 2019, Pakistan's external debt will increase to \$103.4 billion (Rana 2018). By 2022, this forecast projects an external debt of 10%. According to the IMF, Pakistan's significant external debt poses a threat to the country's economy. International businesses find it challenging to conduct business in Pakistan due to its bureaucracy, regulations, and policies. Pakistan is ranked 136th out of 190 countries in the World Bank's 2019 "Ease of Doing Business" report for regulatory performance (Lakhan&Mumtaz,2021). Pakistan does poorly in four areas: obtaining power, upholding agreements, its tax structure, and granting building licenses.

Initiative for the Belt and Road and the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor:

The majority of BRI-related activities are now being carried out in Pakistan as part of CPEC, and CPEC's stated goals are in line with China's main BRI policy documents. On the other hand, not all Sino-Pakistani infrastructure projects that could be considered as achieving BRI goals are part of the CPEC. These actions might be regarded as BRI components. Furthermore, there is no assurance that China will participate directly in all initiatives related to the CPEC. The Pakistani government wants to modernize the nation's infrastructure and create a "mechanism for sustainable economic development" through the CPEC. Utilizing China's financial resources, industrial potential, and technological know-how will enable this. In exchange, Beijing will gain access to the Arabian Sea, opening up a secondary commercial route to Southeast Asia's potentially hazardous Malacca Strait. However, similar to the BRI as a whole, there are a number of unique drivers; therefore it is important to avoid exaggerating the significance of large-scale geostrategic projects (Mahmoud& Ali 2022). It is common knowledge in China that government expenditures on physical infrastructure lead to increased economic activity, the maintenance of social order, and increased levels of personal safety. Since that nation has the ability to function as a counterbalance to India in South Asia and as a potential training ground for terrorists of Uyghur ancestry from Xinjiang, Beijing has a considerable stake in guaranteeing the safety of its "all-weather" partner. As a direct result of this, the CPEC was approved since it was deemed to be a crucial strategic commitment. Establishing commercial outlets in Pakistan and satisfying local consumer demands are both essential elements to aiding in the more stable development of China's western heartland. On the ground, the surplus capacity that currently exists within the country's borders is assisting in the advancement of the nation's commercial companies (Standish, 2021). There are moments when it seems as though CPEC's core goal—to deliver prosperity to Pakistan—is at odds with its financial motivation. This is due to CPEC being a business venture. Chinese companies have frequently been successful in obtaining long-term contractual rights to manage roads and energy infrastructures as well as collect electricity or toll fees at set pricing that are significantly higher than market rates. Pakistan might be at a competitive disadvantage compared to other countries in the region, notably Bangladesh, because of its current high prices. The CPEC was and remains a fascinating bet, but there are only ten years left for the project to complete its alleged aim of transforming Pakistan into a thriving regional commercial centre (Nurmuhammedov,2017).

Pakistan's importance of the Gwadar port:

Get rid of Pakistan's energy shortage completely. Pakistan is thought to lose between 4,000 and 7,000 megawatts (MW) of electricity per year as a result of its poor infrastructure, unmet energy needs, and inadequate power generation (Gholizadeh and Madani 2020). Since energy shortages and frequent power outages cost as much as 7% of GDP, there is a clear correlation between economic progress, improved human well-being, and even the advancement of national security. It will resolve Pakistan's energy crisis and make up for the nation's underlying shortage of power and energy because 76% of CPEC-related projects are in the energy industry. China wants to add 17,000 MW of new electricity-generating capacity to Pakistan by investing roughly \$34 billion in the country's energy sector. Pakistan is expected to get up to 10,400 MW of electricity from CPEC after the initial projects are completed (Gholizadeh&Madani 2020). Because it examines how geography and economics influence a regional power's foreign policy, geo-economics is a crucial component of the study of international relations (Rafiq, 2020).

Supporting Pakistan's economic expansion:

There are 51 areas of cooperation between China and Pakistan, including those in the fields of transportation, agriculture, energy, marine, media, health, finance, trade research, and education. Pakistan is currently developing and implementing infrastructure projects at a cost of \$46 billion. The GDP of Pakistan is about 20% covered by this. Since 1970, this amount of money has represented all foreign investment in Pakistan (Gholizadeh&Madani 2020). One of Pakistan's highest priority projects is the modernization of the Karachi to Peshawar railway, which the Asian Development Bank (ADB) has pledged to fund with \$8 billion (Javaid ,

2016). Rail transport accounts for 75% of all freight and passenger traffic in Pakistan. The normal travel time for passengers would increase from 65 to 160 kilometers per hour after the train upgrading project is complete. Additionally, it will increase its current transit capacity by twofold to 8%. (Tribune , 2019).Pakistan will become a hub for trade and business in the Middle East, which is a beneficial effect. If and when South Asia, Africa, the Middle East, West Asia, Central Asia, and East Asia are connected, Pakistan stands to benefit greatly in tax income and as a hub for the convergence and spread of people, logistics, and information. The World Bank estimates that Pakistan's merchandise exports to its neighbors alone will rise to \$58 billion annually after infrastructure projects are finished in 2019, a threefold increase over exports currently made (Gholizadeh&Madani 2020).

Geographic positioning and strategic space:

Previously allies and supporters in the fight against terrorism, the United States of America and Pakistan now have a wide variety of differences. Pakistan takes issue, in particular, with the United States' sanctions and arms embargo against Pakistan over its nuclear Programme, both of which prompted India to join the Nuclear Suppliers Group (NSG) and conduct related business.Pakistan believes that India and Pakistan have been treated unfairly by the United States when it comes to the problem of nuclear proliferation. Pakistan claims that when it comes to the problem of nuclear proliferation, the US regards Pakistan and India differently. On the other side, the killing of Osama bin Laden and the deployment of drones in Pakistan have both heightened tensions in Pakistan and led to an increase in anti-American sentiment in the United States (Iqbal, 2016).The United States is pressing India to become more integrated into what it refers to as the "Asia-Pacific rebalance," after turning its focus away from South Asia, in the hopes that it will provide a fresh source of regional stability. India has been striving considerably harder to maintain its position as the dominant power in the Indian Ocean and throughout South Asia since Modi gained office.There is currently an agreement in place for Afghanistan, Iran, and India to build a modern port away from the Persian Gulf. The expansion of trade ties between India and Afghanistan in the area of South and Central Asia surrounding Pakistan will benefit from this. The United States, India, and Arab nations' closer ties have reduced Pakistan's regional importance, which has also increased the likelihood that Pakistan will be surrounded from both the east and the west.The CPEC could help reduce some of the strategic tension that results from Pakistan's proximity to both the US and India by enhancing its geographic advantages (Hussain&Hussain 2022). Based on the port of Gwadar, Pakistan has the chance to establish bilateral and multilateral ties with additional countries and give locals another access point to the sea.Pakistan's reliance on Karachi, the nation's most important commercial port at the moment, may be lessened with the construction of a port in Gwadar. The Karachi Port is currently in charge of managing more than 60% of all of Pakistan's marine trade with the rest of the globe. An increase in hostilities with India or even a new military confrontation might affect Pakistan's economy and cause problems in the commercial sector in Karachi.These two scenarios are both conceivable. The recent military conflict between Pakistan and India in 2019 made it clearly clear that Pakistan needs to build the Gwadar port in order to boost the economic security of the nation. 2019 was the year of this fight.The Indian Minister of Defense issued a harsh warning, recalling the experiences of 1964 and 1971, and warned Pakistan that it risked being destroyed on its own country. Regarding the hostilities that erupted between India and Pakistan in 1964 and 1971, he said thus. Reducing Pakistan's reliance on the Karachi port might give the country better access to free water and increase its economic stability, especially in light of the ongoing issues in ties between Pakistan and India.

Development of the Gwadar port is necessary for economic security:

Pakistan has six ports in total, two of which enjoy advantageous topographical characteristics. The two ports that are located on the eastern and western corners of the nation, respectively, are Karachi Port and Gwadar Port. On the country's eastern edge is where Karachi Port is situated. Around 1046 kilometers of shoreline stretch along Pakistan's southernmost region (Salman &Habib 2020).While Gwadar Port can be found on the western side, close to Iran, Karachi Port may be found close to the border with India. During Pakistan's colonial era, the foundations for what would eventually grow to be the nation's most significant commercial and military port were constructed. Karachi Port has become Pakistan's principal port as a result. Pakistan's most populated metropolis, Karachi, also doubles as the nation's main hub for business, trade, and finance. Additionally, it is the location of the Pakistani Naval Command, which is situated in Karachi, the city where the port is situated. During the third India-Pakistan War in 1964, the Indian Navy was able to successfully block it because to the lack of security depth at this point. India attempted yet again to take over the port city of Karachi during the conflict that erupted in 1971. The Indian army was able to achieve their objective of destroying a sizable portion of the port's infrastructure, in addition to a huge number of commercial ships and fuel supplies, thanks to the two naval attacks that they carried out. Pakistan has been working to make the more functional since 1964 in order to develop the area's potential as a commercial port.Due to China's extensive internal and external security measures, the port is of the utmost importance. Additionally, the port may be located close to the Persian Gulf, the entry to the Strait of Hormuz, and the beach of the Arabian Sea. Being the third-largest port in the entire world adds to its significance.This adds to the overall importance of it. Beijing is placing more emphasis on

Gwadar Port as a result of China's desire to increase its access to the Indian Ocean. This is due to the intention of the Chinese government. Additionally, it looks that the Middle Eastern oil storage industry will benefit significantly from the port's expansion. This is due to the fact that the port is located close to a number of important maritime routes, which are the routes used by the vast bulk of oil exports worldwide. For instance, it is believed that almost 40% of China's imported oil is transported across the Strait of Hormuz, which is less than 500 kilometers away from the port of Gwadar (Kardon ,2020).

The value of the Gwadar port to China:

Beijing and Islamabad agree that Gwadar Port is significant from a military and geopolitical standpoint in this regard. The Gwadar Port in Pakistan's Baluchistan Province also plays a big part in the area. China may use this region as a geostrategic hub for its military, political, and economic activities in the North Indian Ocean. China is interested in purchasing Gwadar for a number of reasons, not the least of which is to win India's favors. This is so because Gwadar is where the port is situated. In addition to being a port of entry, the Chinese government views Gwadar Port as a place to monitor marine activity in both the Arabian Sea and the Indian Ocean (Ebrahim , 2021). The Gwadar Port project appears to be Beijing's main focus, despite the fact that CPEC is linked to a number of other infrastructure initiatives. Consider the fact that China converted a 230 million dollar loan into a grant in 2015 as part of the construction of Gwadar Airport as evidence of the significance of this connection (Caliskan ,2022).). Additionally, China has agreed to grant a loan to Pakistan in the amount of \$140 million to be used for the construction of a highway connecting Gwadar to the route that follows the Pakistani shore (News 2015). The loan will not be subject to interest. Beijing, on the other hand, has adopted a distinctive strategy with regard to the CPEC's remaining projects. The Gwadar Port is built to hold three ships with a combined capacity of 50,000 tones, and the maximum length for each ship is 200 m, as it is anticipated that China will grant access to the aforementioned seas via Gwadar (Kanwal, 2018). 91 percent of the port's revenue would be China Overseas Ports Holding Company's to keep, according to reports from the management of the Port of Islamabad. The China Overseas Ports Holding Company will also be in charge of running the port's business operations. The port is expected to have the ability to handle 137 thousand container loads and 868 thousand general commodities annually (Shahzad ,2019). Additionally, there is a chance that China could establish its upcoming overseas military presence there. The port's location puts it close to the Persian Gulf, the Indian Ocean, and the Strait of Hormuz in addition to China. Physically, China is not far from the port (Malik ,2012).

Conclusion:

Both Western and South Asian nations are subject to these dangers. The execution of this approach is part of Beijing's goal. Building the Gwadar port, which could improve Pakistan's access to open seas, is another factor that boosts the country's growing economic security. Gwadar Port in Pakistan is thought to be where the CPEC's southernmost point is located. The area near Kashgar, China, is thought to be the northernmost point. The strategic geopolitical location of the port of Gwadar will be crucial for Pakistan and China's potential future collaboration. From an energy perspective, the Gwadar port will modify China's main pathways for obtaining oil, and it's feasible that the port will even change China's typical pattern for importing oil. China's main sources of imported crude oil are countries in the Middle East and Russia. The most northern part of the corridor, Kashgar, would become another "Shanghai" in China as a result of the CPEC. Politically, Pakistan and western China are both protected by the CPEC and the Gwadar Port Development Project. The Taliban added to Pakistan's already unstable political environment after leaving Afghanistan. As mentioned in an article published in a newspaper that focuses on international issues, it is not improbable that terrorists may acquire nuclear weapons and technology if the situation in Pakistan worsens. In addition, because China and Pakistan are geographical neighbors, the issue of national security is extremely important to both of these nations. As soon as extremists in that nation gain a stronghold in its society, the government of Pakistan will no longer be able to guarantee the entire protection of western China. It's conceivable that this is where the expression "if Pakistan catches fire, it will damage China" came from. The BRI's main point is the port of Gwadar, which is the CPEC's southernmost point. The so-called "corridor effect" will be helpful for Pakistan's overall economic development. Radicals on the surface will find it much harder to obtain nuclear weapons and nuclear technology as a direct result of Pakistan's move towards economic modernisation. China's western security is no longer at risk from external threats. This is done in order to provide the western part of our country a voice in economic politics and protect its security.

References

Bhatti, Baber Ali. Ports and Their Importance for Pakistan. 2020.

Caliskan, Goktug. Increasing Strategic Importance of Gwadar Port: Will It Become China's New Military Base? Ankara: Ankara Center for Crisis and Policy Studies, 2022.

Desk, News. Strategic Significance of Pakistan's Gwadar Port in the region | By MD Pathik Hasan. 2021.

- Ebrahim, Zofeen. Pakistan's key CPEC port a long way from trade hub vision. 2021.
- Gholizadeh, Ali, and Seyedashkan Madani. "Ageo-economic and geopolitical review of Gwadar Port on belt and road initiative." *Maritime Business Review*, 2020: 335-349.
- Haider, Mehtab. Pakistan's debt, liabilities touch Rs 29.861 trillion. 2018.
- Hussain, Iqtidar, and Israr Hussain. "The Effect of China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) on Regional Geopolitics." *Geopolitics Quarterly*, 2022: 206-230.
- Iqbal, Anwar. US expresses concern over security of Pakistan's N-weapons. 2016.
- Javaid, Umbreen. "Assessing CPEC: Potential Threats and Prospects." *Pakistan Economic and Social Review*, 2016: 123-142.
- Kanwal, Gurmeet. Pakistan's Gwadar Port: A New Naval Base in China's String of Pearls in the Indo-Pacific. 2018.
- Kardon, Isaac B. China Maritime Report No. 7: Gwadar: China's Potential Strategic. China Maritime Studies Institute, 2020.
- Lakhan, Allah Bux, and Jazib Mumtaz. "Ease of Doing Business in Pakistan." *PalArch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology*, 2021: 4928-4934.
- Mahmood, Shahid, and Ghaffar Ali. "Belt and road initiative as a catalyst of infrastructure development: Assessment of resident's perception and attitude towards China-Pakistan Economic Corridor." *PLoS ONE*, 2022.
- Malik, Hasan Yaser. "Strategic Importance of Gwadar Port." *Journal of Political Studies*, 2012.
- Mardell, Jacob. "The BRI in Pakistan: China's flagship economic corridor." *MERICSMercator Institute for China Studies*, 2020.
- News, The. China converts \$230m loan for Gwadar airport into grant. 2015.
- Nurmuhammedov, Nurmyrat. "China-Pakistan Economic Corridor and Its Geostrategic Importance in Terms of Belt and Road Initiative." *Afro Eurasian Studies Journal*, 2017: 34-64.
- Rafiq, Muhammad. Economic & Strategic Significance of Gwadar Port. 2020.
- Rana, Shahbaz. Pakistan's external debt to climb to \$103b by June 2019: IMF report. 2018.
- Report, Annual. Military and Security Developments Involving the People's Republic of China 2020. OFFICE OF THE SECRETARY OF DEFENSE, 2020.
- Salim, Muhammad, and Summer Sultana. "Gwadar and its Importance for Pakistan and China." *BALUCHISTAN REVIEW*, 2019: 301-313.
- Shahzad, S M. "Gwadar Port Growing Beyond Economic Glory." *International Journal of Multidisciplinary and Current Research*, 2019.
- Shang, Yunfeng, and Abdul Hameed Pitafi. "Assessing the Impact of Community Factors on Local Community Support for Tourism: An Empirical Investigation of the China-Pakistan-Economic Corridor." *Frontiers in Psychology*, 2022.
- Smith, Sheila A. The Quad in the Indo-Pacific: What to Know. 2021.
- Standish, Reid. What Pakistan's Relationship With China Tells Us About The Belt And Road Initiative. 2021.
- Tribune, Express. ML-1 to be completed in five years. 2019.

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